

Exploring the Influence of Creative Leadership and Organizational Culture towards School Heads' Performance

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Abstract: This study explores the influence of creative leadership and organizational culture on the performance of school heads. A total of 398 public school teachers from Davao Region, the Philippines, participated in the survey. This cross-sectional descriptive survey utilized adapted survey questionnaires to determine school heads' creative leadership competence level, the strength of the organizational culture, and overall performance from the perspectives of teachers. The findings indicate that school heads are highly rated in creative leadership dimensions – imagination, flexibility, and vision. Teachers also perceived that public schools maintain a strong organizational culture characterized by effective change management, goal achievement, teamwork, cultural strength, and customer orientation. The performance of school heads was also assessed with high competent rating in instructional supervision, professional development, and management behavior. However, the present study found that the direct influence of creative leadership and organizational culture on school heads' performance is limited, suggesting that additional factors such as resource availability, external policy influences, or individual leader characteristics may play a critical role. The results underscore the need for a comprehensive approach to leadership development and further research to fully understand the determinants of effective school management in dynamic educational settings.

Keywords: creative leadership, organizational culture, school management, school heads.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapidly changing educational landscape in the 21st century necessitates school leaders who can navigate complex challenges with innovation, adaptability, and visionary practices. Educational leadership is increasingly recognized as a critical factor in enhancing school performance and fostering student achievement (Leithwood et al., 2020). According to Peregrino et al. (2021), a school's ability to provide high-quality instruction is greatly dependent on its school leaders. In addition to managing and guiding high-quality teaching practices, these leaders assume multiple roles, as managers, facilitators, and educational leaders, ensuring that all procedures are followed, and that staff operate successfully, efficiently, and cooperatively. Effective school leadership goes beyond administrative tasks; it involves guiding teachers toward improved performance, maintaining high standards in core instructional areas, and fostering ongoing school development (Saleem et al., 2022; Yousaf et al., 2018).

In this context, creative leadership has emerged as an essential competency. It empowers school heads not only to manage routine tasks but also to reimagine educational practices, inspire staff and students, and cultivate an environment conducive to continuous learning (Beghetto & Kaufman, 2014). Creative leadership is characterized by the ability to generate and implement innovative solutions to challenges, foster a culture of creativity and collaboration, and encourage individuals to reach their full potential (Al-Zoubi et al., 2023; Nwachukwu & Hieu, 2020). Moreover, research indicates that teacher effectiveness is significantly impacted by leadership styles, with creative leadership offering strategies that embrace change and drive both qualitative and quantitative advancements in institutional performance (Arivayagan & Pihie, 2017; Al Ta'ani, 2022).

Parallel to the development of creative leadership competencies is the significance of organizational culture. A positive organizational culture has the potential to elevate the motivation, commitment, and satisfaction of both teachers and students, ultimately enhancing the quality of teaching and learning experiences (De La Cruz, 2019).

Despite the growing emphasis on creative leadership and its demonstrated impact on teaching practices and student outcomes, the interplay between a leader's creative competence, the prevailing organizational culture, and overall professional competence remains underexplored. While existing studies have shown significant relationships between school administrators' instructional leadership skills and both teachers' performance and self-efficacy (Daing & Mustapha, 2023), there is a notable empirical gap concerning the joint influence of creative leadership and organizational culture on school heads' performance. Previous research has predominantly focused on the impact of professional competencies on organizational culture, with little attention given to evaluating the combined effect of creative leadership and organizational culture on educational leadership outcomes.

Within this framework, the present study aims to fill this gap by investigating the creative leadership of school heads in the Davao Region, the prevailing organizational culture in public schools, and exploring how these factors collectively relate to, and potentially predict, the school heads' performance. By integrating insights from creative leadership theory, organizational culture research, and professional competence frameworks, this study seeks not only to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to effective educational leadership but also to identify areas where further research is needed. The outcomes of this research are expected to offer valuable implications for designing tailored leadership development programs and informing policy initiatives aimed at enhancing school performance in similar educational contexts.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of creative leadership of the school heads in Davao Region assessed by teachers?
2. What is the extent of the organizational culture in different public schools in Davao Region as assessed by teachers?
3. What is the level of school heads' performance?
4. To what extent do creative leadership and organizational culture correlates on school heads' performance?
5. What is the significant relationship between creative leadership and organizational culture to school heads' performance?

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed descriptive correlational design to determine the extent of school heads creative leadership, organizational culture and their professional competency. Correlational research is useful when the goal is to examine the relationships between two or more random variables within the same population or between the same variables in two different populations (Curtis et al., 2016). It tests the relationships without altering individual variables or arbitrarily assigning participants to various environments. According to (Diab et al., 2019), correlation does not imply causation; a correlational design looks at relationship.

Sampling

The study included 398 school teachers selected using cluster sampling from the eleven divisions within the Davao Region. Participant distribution across these divisions was based on their respective population sizes and followed the cluster sampling approach. This method, a type of probability sampling, is commonly used in research involving large and geographically spread-out populations—making it well-suited for covering the schools across Division XI.

Analysis

Quantitative data is used to generate counts and frequencies, and to design computer programs that systematically organize the findings. These results are then presented in tables and graphs, with percentages calculated using appropriate statistical tools.

Mean. This was utilized to address statement problems 1, 2, and 3. Problem 1 involves evaluating the creative leadership qualities of school heads in the Davao Region as perceived by the participants. Problem 2 aims to assess the degree of organizational culture among teachers towards their institution. Problem 3 seeks to determine the extent of school head's performance styles exhibited by the school heads in the Davao Region, as evaluated by the teachers.

Pearson *r*. This was utilized to address statement problem 4 to confirm the significant relationship among creative leadership, organizational culture, and school heads performance.

Multiple Regression Analysis. This addressed problem 5, indicating that both creative leadership and organizational culture are strong predictors of school heads performance. Additionally, it also resolved problem 6, confirming that these leadership styles significantly influence the school heads performance.

Data collected from the survey instruments were encoded and managed in Microsoft Excel 365. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques in IBM SPSS Statistics 27. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were calculated for each construct to provide an overview of the levels of creative leadership, organizational culture, and professional competence as perceived by the teachers. Additionally, Pearson correlation analyses were conducted to examine the relationships between creative leadership competence, organizational culture, and professional competence. To further explore the predictive relationships among these variables, linear regression analysis was performed. All statistical analyses were conducted at a significance level of 0.05.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

School Heads' Creative Leadership Competence

Table 1 shows the competence level of creative leadership among school heads in Davao Region as perceived by their teachers. The results revealed an overall high level of creative leadership with a mean score of 4.45 (SD = 0.254). This finding reflects a strong collective validation of the innovative capabilities and leadership practices of school heads. Teachers recognize that these leaders play a vital role in fostering a culture of creativity, critical thinking, and adaptability within their schools.

Table 1. Level of Creative Leadership Competence.

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Imagination	4.51	0.387	Highly Competent
Flexibility	4.45	0.314	Highly Competent
Vision	4.41	0.373	Highly Competent
Overall	4.45	0.254	Highly Competent

In terms of specific dimensions of creative leadership, the domain of *imagination* had the highest mean score of 4.51 (SD = 0.387). This result implies that school heads are particularly effective in generating innovative ideas, thinking creatively, and envisioning novel solutions to educational challenges. In addition, the dimension of *flexibility* received a high rating (Mean = 4.45, SD = 0.314), indicating that school heads are adept at adapting to change, embracing new ideas, and adjusting their strategies to meet emerging needs.

The dimension of *vision* also contributed to the overall positive perception of creative leadership, with a mean score of 4.41 (SD = 0.373). This suggests that school heads are proficient in setting clear, strategic goals and inspiring both staff and students with a positive outlook for the future. These results underscore that school heads in the Davao Region are recognized as highly competent creative leaders, whose practices are essential for promoting innovative instructional strategies and continuous school improvement.

Level of Organizational Culture in Public Schools

Table 2 shows the level of organizational culture as perceived by the respondents. The overall level of organizational culture in public schools of Davao Region was rated as very high, with a mean score of 4.35 (SD = 0.631). This finding indicates that public schools possess a strong organizational culture characterized by shared values, beliefs, and behaviors among staff and students. Teachers' responses suggest that such a culture is fundamental in promoting effective collaboration and a productive work environment.

Table 2. Level of Organizational Culture in Public Schools.

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Managing Change	4.39	0.538	Very High
Achieving Goals	4.35	0.536	Very High
Coordinating Team	4.31	0.425	Very High
Cultural Strength	4.26	0.521	Very High
Customer Orientation	4.28	0.546	Very High
Overall	4.35	0.631	Very High

Specifically, the dimension of **managing change** was rated at a mean of 4.39 (SD = 0.538), reflecting that public schools maintain a positive attitude toward change and demonstrate a readiness to embrace new ideas and practices. The ability to **achieve goals** was also rated very high (Mean = 4.35, SD = 0.536), suggesting that these schools exhibit a strong sense of purpose and commitment to accomplishing shared objectives. These dimensions are indicative of an organizational culture that is both dynamic and results-oriented.

Additional dimensions further reinforce the overall assessment. The capacity for **coordinating team** efforts achieved a mean score of 4.31 (SD = 0.425), underscoring the emphasis on effective communication, cooperation, and teamwork within the schools. Moreover, the constructs of **cultural strength** (Mean = 4.26, SD = 0.521) and **customer orientation** (Mean = 4.28, SD = 0.546) highlight the schools' strong shared identity and their commitment to meeting the needs of parents and students. These findings collectively suggest that public schools in the region have established a healthy and supportive organizational culture.

Level of School Heads' Performance

The performance of school heads, as assessed by teachers, is also remarkably high (shown in Table 4). The overall mean score for performance was 4.38 (SD = 0.363), which reflects a strong foundation of knowledge, skills, and abilities in educational leadership among the school heads. This rating confirms that, in addition to their creative leadership qualities, school heads are proficient in managing key administrative and instructional responsibilities.

In terms of dimensions of performance, **instructional supervision** was rated at a mean of 4.34 (SD = 0.536), suggesting that school heads are effective in monitoring teaching practices, providing constructive feedback, and fostering teacher development. The dimension of **professional development practice** received a mean score of 4.39 (SD = 0.477), indicating that these leaders are successful in promoting continuous professional learning and offering relevant staff development opportunities. These results are consistent with the view that strong leadership directly contributes to the professional growth of teaching staff.

Table 3. Level of School Head’s Performance in Davao Region

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Instructional Supervision	4.34	0.536	Highly Competent
Professional Development Practice	4.39	0.477	Highly Competent
Management Behavior	4.39	0.426	Highly Competent
Overall	4.34	0.536	Highly Competent

In addition, the dimension of **management behavior** was also highly rated, with a mean of 4.39 (SD = 0.426). This finding suggests that school heads are competent in organizing, planning, directing, and controlling school resources and operations effectively. These results affirm that school heads are not only creative and adaptive leaders but also excel in professional competencies essential for the efficient management of school operations.

Relationship of the Creative Leadership Competence and Organizational Culture towards School Heads’ Performance

Table 4 examines the relationship of creative leadership competence and organizational culture with the performance of the school head. The analysis indicates that the correlation between school heads’ performance and creative leadership is $r = 0.0176$ ($p = 0.7268$), while the correlation between school heads’ performance and organizational culture is $r = 0.0693$ ($p = 0.1677$). Both p-values are greater than the 0.05 significance level, suggesting that these relationships are not statistically significant.

The lack of significant correlation implies that neither creative leadership competence nor organizational culture, as measured in this study, have a strong linear association with the performance outcome of school heads. Despite high ratings in creative leadership and organizational culture, these factors do not appear to translate directly into improved performance of school heads, based on teachers’ assessment.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis of Creative Leadership Competence and Organizational Culture towards Professional Competence of School Heads.

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	r	p
School Heads’ Performance	Creative Leadership of School Heads	0.0176	0.7268
	Schools’ Organizational Culture	0.0693	0.1677

Effects of Creative Leadership Competence and Organizational Culture on School Heads’ Performance

To further investigate the predictive influence of creative leadership competence and organizational culture on the performance of school heads, a linear regression analysis was conducted. Table 5 shows that the regression model did not yield a statistically significant relationship between the independent variables, creative leadership competence and organizational culture, and the dependent variable, school head performance, as evidenced by an F-value of 0.9632 and a p-value of 0.3826.

Table 5. F-Test for Regression Relation.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Regression	0.2534	2	0.1267	0.9632	0.3826
Residual	51.9602	395	0.1315		
Total	52.2136	397			

The regression analysis indicates that the combined effect of creative leadership competence and organizational culture does not significantly predict the performance of school heads. The estimated coefficients for the independent variables (shown in Table 6) were not statistically significant, with p-values exceeding the 0.05 level of significance. Although the intercept was significant, it does not contribute to understanding the influence of the predictors.

Table 6. The Estimated Coefficients in the Linear Regression Model.

	Coefficients	se	t	p
(Intercept)	3.9610	0.3941	10.0514	< 0.001
Creative Leadership	0.0104	0.0726	0.1438	0.8857
Organizational Culture	0.0867	0.0646	1.3431	0.1800

The regression results confirm that, based on the data collected from 398 public school teachers, creative leadership competence and schools' organizational culture do not have a statistically significant effect on the performance outcome of school heads. This suggests that other variables may play a more pivotal role in determining performance, highlighting the need for further research to explore additional factors that might influence school heads' performance.

V. DISCUSSION

Creative Leadership of School Heads

The findings of this study indicate that school heads in the Davao Region are widely recognized by teachers as possessing strong creative leadership qualities. This aligns with previous research showing that effective creative leadership is essential for fostering environments that encourage innovation and adaptability in schools (Saglam & Ucar, 2022). In particular, the emphasis on imaginative leadership, as highlighted by Judson and Dougherty (2024), suggests that when school heads harness their imaginative capacities, they are better able to envision possibilities beyond current limitations, thereby creating opportunities for innovative instructional strategies.

In addition, the leadership dimensions of flexibility and vision play a crucial role in meeting emerging challenges and setting strategic directions. A study by Raptis et al. (2021) underscores that imaginative leadership distinguishes itself from traditional models by placing creativity at its core, thereby enabling leaders to inspire their school communities. Similarly, the work of Cheng (2023) reinforces that imaginative capability is a cornerstone of visionary leadership in school management. These qualities support a collaborative and adaptive school environment, where open communication and a readiness to embrace change drive continuous improvement.

Furthermore, the observed creative leadership among school heads resonates with findings by Kristiono & Fachrunnisa (2017), who emphasized that improved organizational performance is driven by a synergy between innovative leadership and employee solidarity. The capacity to blend visionary thinking with practical adaptability, as also noted by Bagwell (2020) and Fitriani (2023), indicates that effective school leadership in the Davao Region is not only about generating creative ideas but also about implementing them in ways that respond to the dynamic demands of modern education. This multifaceted approach is vital for sustaining a culture that encourages learning and growth within schools (Aloraifan, 2021).

Organizational Culture in Public Schools

The study's results suggest that public schools in the region exhibit a robust organizational culture, a finding that aligns with previous research emphasizing the importance of shared values and collective beliefs in educational settings (De La Cruz, 2019). A strong organizational culture, as described by Pavlidou and Efstathiades (2021), provides a foundation for establishing norms and practices that enhance collaboration and institutional cohesion. This cultural strength appears to facilitate a supportive work environment where effective teamwork and communication are prioritized.

In addition, the role of customer orientation and a focus on achieving shared goals further highlight the impact of organizational culture on school performance. Studies by Lewis and King (2016) have shown that when schools integrate core values with strategic planning, they tend to experience enhanced productivity and improved student outcomes. Moreover, research by Welborn (2019) and Beycioglu and Kondakci (2021) indicates that schools which adapt to changes in their organizational environment are better positioned to meet evolving educational demands and foster a sense of belonging among staff and students.

The evidence from this study also mirrors findings by Ali (2017) and Samon et al. (2023), who documented that a positive school culture not only shapes individual behaviors but also reinforces a collective identity that drives school success. In

addition, Paredes-saavedra et al. (2024) and Brun et al. (2020) demonstrated that a collaborative organizational culture enhances staff engagement and communication, leading to improved institutional performance. These insights suggest that the high level of organizational culture observed in the Davao Region contributes to the overall stability and effectiveness of schools, setting the stage for continuous improvement.

School Heads' Performance and Its Relationships with Creative Leadership and Organizational Culture

The professional competence of school heads, as perceived by teachers, reflects a comprehensive skill set in areas such as instructional supervision, professional development, and management behavior. This is consistent with previous findings by Aquino et al. (2021) and Lepardo and Caingcoy (2021), who noted that core leadership competencies significantly influence school performance. Effective supervisory practices, for instance, have been linked to improved teacher performance and student outcomes (Misllang-Sison & Junio, 2019; Naguit, 2024), highlighting the critical role that proficient school leaders play in enhancing overall educational quality.

Despite the high ratings in both creative leadership and organizational culture, the study found that these factors did not have a significant direct impact on the professional competence of school heads. This observation is supported by research that suggests the relationship between leadership practices and professional competencies can be complex and mediated by other contextual factors (Cabigao, 2019; Viador, 2024). For example, while creative leadership and a strong organizational culture are important, they may interact with additional variables such as resource availability, external pressures, and individual leader characteristics to ultimately influence professional competence (Perez & Banayo, 2023; Baluyos et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the findings indicate that while effective leadership behaviors such as instructional supervision and management practices are vital, they may operate independently of the broader creative and cultural dimensions. As reported by Thawinkarn et al. (2018) and further supported by studies on adaptive leadership (Lou, 2024; Bagwell, 2020), the direct influence of leadership on professional competence might require a complex investigation. Additional determinants of school head performance may be further identified. In general, these findings emphasize that while creative leadership and a robust organizational culture are integral to fostering a positive educational environment, their direct translation into professional competence remains an area for future investigation.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study examined the influence of creative leadership and organizational culture in shaping the performance of school heads in the Davao Region. The findings reveal that school heads are well-regarded for their creative leadership, particularly in terms of imagination, flexibility, and vision. Likewise, public schools exhibit a strong organizational culture characterized by effective change management, clear goal setting, teamwork, and a commitment to meeting the needs of their stakeholders.

However, while the presence of creative leadership and a robust organizational culture is evident, their direct impact on school heads' performance appears limited. This suggests that additional factors may also be important in influencing the performance of school heads. These results indicate that creative leadership and a positive organizational culture are necessary, but not solely sufficient, for enhancing the overall performance of school heads.

In light of these findings, it is recommended that policymakers and educational administrators adopt a comprehensive approach to leadership development. Efforts should not only focus on strengthening creative and adaptive leadership skills but also on addressing other factors that may improve school heads' performance. Future initiatives could include targeted professional development programs and improved resource support, as well as further research to better understand the full range of factors influencing effective educational leadership.

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International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 12, Issue 2, pp: (18-27), Month: March - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

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